

Chemical Examination of the Roots of *Gymnosporia spinosa* (Forsk)

K. Satyanarayana and Rajendra Kumar Mishra

Gymnosporia spinosa (Forsk) belonging to the Celastraceae family is a shrub which is commonly called Baikal in Hindi. It is cultivated in Punjab, Madhya Pradesh and Bihar. In Ayurvedic medicine the plant has been described as cure for snake bites, ulcers and 'Kapha'. We became interested to undertake a chemical investigation of the whole plant of *Gymnosporia spinosa*, since no investigation on it was reported in the literature. The present communication on the roots of the plant revealed the presence of β -amyrin and dulcitol. In addition to these two substances a quinone which could not be crystallised was also isolated from both the extractions. Further work is under progress.

Shade dried roots (450 g.) were powdered and extracted successively with petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) and dilute alcohol. The light petroleum extract was concentrated and saponified with alcoholic potassium hydroxide. The unsaponifiable matter was separated and subjected to chromatography over Brockmann alumina using light petroleum, benzene, chloroform and their mixtures as eluents. The petroleum/benzene (3:2 and 1:1) eluates furnished a white crystalline solid.

The white solid was crystallised from chloroform-methanol mixture (1:1) in needles (1.5 g.); m.p. 194-196°; (α)_D²⁵ + 87° · 0 (chloroform). (Found: C, 83.94; H, 11.69; Calc. for C₃₀H₅₀O: C, 84.43; H, 11.82%). The substance gave a positive Burchard-Liebermann reaction for a triterpene. It was eventually identified as β amyryl. The identity was further confirmed by mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of β amyryl and from the preparation of benzoate derivative², m.p. 232-233°.

The dilute alcohol extract furnished a white crystalline solid. The compound separated out during the course of extraction itself. It could be purified further by one crystallisation from water. It was eventually identified as dulcitol (galactitol) CH₂OH. (CHOH)₄. CH₂OH (m.p. and m.m.p. 187-188°). Further confirmation of the material as dulcitol was obtained by the formation of the hexa-acetyl derivative which after crystallisation from alcohol has m.p. and m.m.p. 168-169°³.

1. K. R. Kirtikar and B. D. Basu, Indian Medicinal Plants, L. M. Basu, Allahabad, 1933, **1**, 577,
2. L. C. King, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 1168.
3. *Nature*, 1949, **164**, 1093,

The authors desire to thank Shri R. Shukla, 'Anchal' Principal, Prof. S. G. Tandon, Chemistry Department, College of Science, Raipur for providing laboratory facilities and also Dr. M. K. Jain, Indiana University, U.S.A. for the supply of authentic samples and microanalysis.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
RAIPUR, (M. P.)

Received, November 20, 1967.